

MOBILE MARKETING: AN INSTRUMENT FOR STRUCTURE CUSTOMER LOYALTY

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ABSTRACT

As of late, advertising to clients has turned out to be progressively testing as the number of accessible items and administrations crosswise over businesses has developed fundamentally, while at the same time showcasing strategies and client touch focuses have multiplied. It is key for the survival of any association to have steadfast clients as the many-sided quality and the intensity in the commercial center respects to what organizations need to do and how they do it, addressing with the necessities of the client.

The current fast development of the cell phone advertise has made versatile promoting one of the most vital publicizing instruments and contact directs accessible toward organizations today. Mobile promoting can expand client steadfastness by giving clients convenient and educational data.

The point of this bit of research means to investigate portable advertising and how it can contribute to client steadfastness. The examination was led to recognize the fundamental techniques for portable advertising utilized by organizations, to distinguish how much contact is pushed on clients by organizations, decide the view of versatile advertising and general decide how portable promoting contributes to client dependability and build up how organizations can enhance the usage of portable advertising.

Keywords: Methods used by Companies, Customer Loyalty, Customer perceptions.

INTRODUCTION

The Cellular Operators Association of India (COAI) has released the latest mobile subscriber numbers for the month ending August 2017. According to the data, telecom service providers had a combined total of 948.54 million subscribers by the end of August, down from 954.95 million in July. The numbers also include those of the new entrant in the Indian telecom space Reliance Jio till the end of July 2017, COAI said.

In the upcoming years, e-commerce is expected to boom in the Asian region. The number of digital buyers in Asia Pacific is projected to pass the one billion mark for the first time in 2018, which will account for 60 percent of all internet users in the region. In line with the regional growth, India, a fast-growing emerging Asian market, shows optimistic projections for the e-commerce industry.

Today, the mobile phone is central to the lives of most consumers, including the lives of young teens. It is a device many consumers cannot seem to do without; they always have it on and check it almost everywhere they go. For these consumers, the mobile phone is not only a personal device used to stay connected with friends and family, but also an extension of their personality and individuality (Grant and O’Donohoe, 2007).

Mobile marketing is still in its early stages, and mobile marketing practices will likely go through fundamental changes as the technology continues to evolve. Research on mobile marketing is also in its early stages, but the literature is growing (Karjaluoto et al. 2008).

Innovation of technology

In recent years, marketing to customers has become increasingly challenging as the number of available products and services across industries has grown significantly, while at the same time marketing tactics and customer touch points have proliferated. The continuing fragmentation of media and information overload has led customers to become less and less interested in companies’ brand messages when delivered through traditional media (Singh et al. 2008).

Technology supports the tasks of reaching customers and satisfying specific needs, which increases the demand for more sophisticated models of market segmentation and customisation. Technologies advances influence customer relationship management to the extent that gathering customer information, interacting with customers, and, eventually, building relationships with them become easier (Smith, 2006).

A. Internet

The spread of the internet has changed the way people conduct their daily activities and browsing and reading information online has become an integral part of people’s lives. Many consumers now spend more time online than viewing television (Truong et al. 2010). In general online advertising inspires greater trust and is perceived as less irritating than advertising in conventional media. Interactivity enables users to adapt the advertisement to their needs, decide whether to read it or not, determine the time spent reading it, access the information immediately and freely choose the page they wish to be displayed (Martín- Santana and Beerli-Palacio, 2012).

B. Social Media

The emergence of Internet-based social media has made it possible for one person to communicate with hundreds or even thousands of other people about products and the companies that provide them. The content timing and frequency of the social media-based conversations occurring between consumers are outside manager’s control in contrast to traditional integrated marketing communications, whereby a high degree of control was present (Mangold and Faulds, 2009).

Montgomery and Chester (2009), state that adolescents are growing up at the centre of an exploding digital media culture. According to a 2007 survey by the Pew Internet and American Life Project, night three percent of teens use the Internet, and more of them than ever are treating it as a venue

for social interaction'. In many ways, teenagers are the defining users of this new culture, avidly embracing an expanding array of Web sites and digital devices, and forging a new set of cultural practices that are quickly moving into the mainstream. This statistic presents the most popular smartphone activities in India as of January 2017. During a survey, it was found that 49 percent of the respondents accessed social media via mobile.

C. Mobile phone marketing

According to Statista a statistical portal <https://www.statista.com/statistics/467163/forecast-of-smartphone-users-in-india/> shows the number of Smartphone users in India from 2015 to 2022. For 2017, the number of Smartphone users in India is estimated to reach 299.24 million, with the number of Smartphone users worldwide forecast to exceed 2.3 billion users by that time.

People are most receptive to mobile advertising based on location, as well as advertising via MMS, SMS and branded apps. Interest in SMS advertising has declined, but has increased significantly for branded apps. These figures suggest there is enormous potential for mobile phone advertising in the future, with well over a million people at least open to most of the main mobile advertising channels.

Since mobile marketing is able to reach individual consumers in a more personal and interactive manner than other traditional marketing forms, many companies have been invested in developing mobile marketing applications. Such applications, namely mobile marketing platforms and international wireless systems, allow companies to interact with consumers faster with more personalized and customized advertisements (Altuna and Konuk, 2009).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are many definitions of the concepts of wireless marketing or mobile marketing. Gummerus and Pihlström, 2011). Furthermore, while studies theoretically discuss the concept of customer perceived value within the context of disruptive change characterised by the blending of mobile and social media technologies (Larivière et al., 2013;Ström et al., 2014), empirical evidence that demonstrate its constituent components and its influence on consumer behaviour, is lacking. Therefore, there is a need for more theoretical and empirical elaboration on the specific drivers of value creation in mobile social media platforms for brands.

The major impacts of the Internet on retailing are the reduced search costs for the consumer (Bakos, 1997, Lynch & Ariely, 2000), an increasing variety of products offered (Brynjolfsson, Hu & Smith, 2003) lower prices (Brynjolfsson & Smith, 2000), empowering consumers to make better choices for themselves, and increasing the relationship with the purchased brand after purchase (Edelman, 2010).

2.1. Customer Relationship Marketing

According to Ryals (2001) Relationship marketing is concerned with how organisations manage and improve their relationships with customers for long-term profitability. Xu et al. (2002) says the focus of CRM increased companies' abilities to understand the customers' current needs, what they have done in

the past, and what they plan to do in the future to meet their own objectives. The goal is to improve the customer's experience of how they interact with us, which hopefully, in turn, creates more satisfaction, which yields more loyalty, which, ideally, yields more sales of products and services. CRM, which is becoming a topic of increasing importance in marketing, is concerned with using information technology (IT) in implementing relationship marketing strategies.

Namazi (2011) describes mobile marketing as a promotional activity designed to enhance the experience of mobile phone users. For businesses, it can be used to build brand awareness, develop a customer database, drive attendance of events, improve customer loyalty and even to increase revenue through the creation of applications that users are willing to pay for.

Customer Loyalty

It is said that the key factor of customer loyalty is customer satisfaction (Donaldson and O'Toole, 2007). Therefore, companies are struggling to sense, serve, and satisfy the needs of their customers by delivering high quality and value for them (Kotler and Armstrong, 2010) which leads to a high level of customer satisfaction and later loyal customers.

Researchers suggest that customer loyalty can be approached in two different perspectives (Amarsanaa and Anjorin, 2012). These are 'attitude' which involves the individuals' feelings informing their attachment to products, services or the organisation as a whole; and 'behavioural' loyalty involving repeated purchases, expanded purchases, and recommendations. One of the factors that influence customer loyalty is customer satisfaction. How good of a relationship a firm and its customers have does not matter if the customers are not satisfied with the products and services they receive (Amarsanaa and Anjorin, 2012). We can reiterate that the closest device to human beings today is the mobile phone and marketers in every industry have since been leveraging on this (Chen, Hsieh, P.T. et al. 2009, cited by Amarsanaa and Anjorin, 2012).

Level of Contact with Customers

Katsioloudes et al. (2007) conveys the roles which companies play when dealing with customers have been transformed by CRM. Yet, with constant change in the business environment, many companies have remained "behind the curve" in recognising that it is the customer who is now "setting the pace". Stone (2000, p29-38) says customers are reasonable; many are quite realistic about the relationship you are constrained by resources, technology and the problems of managing change. In analysing your customers' views about their relationships with companies, companies must understand that the period during which your customers consider themselves to be in a relationship with you may be quite long. Opportunities to strengthen this relationship occur throughout this period, particularly just before, during and immediately after your transactions with them. In their relationship with you, your customers may distinguish between major contact episodes and less important ones.

Perceptions of Mobile Marketing

According to Persaud and Azhar (2012), the perceived value of mobile marketing, especially location-based marketing (LBM), is that marketing information and offers target consumers personally and within their shopping context, such as when a coupon is sent to consumers via Bluetooth as they enter a store. The ability of consumers to receive marketing messages and offers at any time and based on their location

not only reduces their search costs, but also increases their shopping efficiency while perhaps saving them money through discounts or promotions. The convenience, savings, and value of the information received may influence consumers' perceptions of what they are receiving relative to what they have to give up, which is their privacy when giving permission to receive marketing messages on their mobile phones. However, marketing information and offers sent to consumers simply based on their location that they find irrelevant may cause these consumers to think such marketing efforts are annoying and valueless. Ensuring that consumers get relevant, in-context, useful marketing information and offers based on their location is a key challenge of value-based mobile marketing (Persaud and Azhar, 2012).

Mobile Marketing

According to the Mobile Marketing Association, the worldwide mobile marketing trade association, mobile marketing can be defined as: "a set of practices that enables organizations to communicate and engage with their audience in an interactive and relevant manner through any mobile device or network". A mobile device is a constant companion to the consumer, a gateway to a relationship between the consumer and the retailer, making it an ideal supplementary channel for distance selling and physical retailing (Shan-kar, Venkatesh, Hofacker et al, 2010). An industry study showed that half of US mobile consumers are mobile device shoppers, 10 percent heavy and 40 percent light users (Leo Burnett & Arc Worldwide, 2011).

Together with the developments in mobile technologies, mobile devices affecting corporations' commercial activities and adding new dimensions to consumers' purchase behaviors resulted in the notion of mobile marketing. Such that mobile marketing is a new marketing approach that, makes use of mobile communication technologies in order to go one step ahead in this competitive environment, provide more output with less resources, minimize operational costs by utilizing latest technologies and gain a modern structure (Kocabas, 2005:113). Scharl et.al. (2005: 165) define mobile marketing as a realm in which the wireless consumers are encouraged towards products, utilized free of time and place.

Another definition describe mobile marketing as conveying various marketing activities, specially advertisement messages, sales offers, special offers, sales, raffles, contests, etc. to consumers via mobile devices. The most important feature of the mobile marketing activities performed via mobile devices is the ability to establish voice, text and visual communication with consumers anywhere, any time and the ability to store messages. In order for the corporations to be successful in mobile marketing activities, they need to establish an active communication with consumers.

In an article about the implications of mobile technology on mobile commerce (m-commerce), Balasubramanian, Peterson and Jarvenpaa (2002) described that m-commerce is a form of communication which involves "either one-way or interactive, between two or more humans, between a human (or humans) and one or more inanimate objects or between two or more inanimate objects (e.g., between devices)" (p. 350). These authors used the concepts relating time and space to discuss a conceptualized framework of mobile technology and m-commerce. They explained that buying products and services from a brick and mortar retail shop may discourage a customer who does not know the location of the shop and/or who cannot move around easily due to the geographical distance, time

constraints, and other barriers. However, it is more flexible and convenient for a customer to get information about a product or a service, and to make a purchase of such product or service via his/her mobile, provided that the seller does provide such mobile applications phone (Balasubramanian et al., 2002; Altuna and Konuk, 2009). Although some marketing activities are not available via mobile technologies, space and time are considered constraints to consumers living in a world without mobile technologies.

Permission Based Marketing

Neumann (2005) states the concept of "permission marketing" addresses the widespread problem of spam in new media communication by demanding the explicit agreement of the addressee to receive marketing information. This approach recognises that the majority of anonymous mass advertising is despised by consumers leading them to reject the messages (Godin, 2001) cited by Neumann (2005). Additionally, mobile marketing also requires the customer to provide personal data to the marketer, so that the full benefits of mobile marketing can be put into use. Such personal data may include demographic and location information. The more companies can utilise various kinds of customer data, the more personalised, relevant and effective their mobile marketing is likely to be (Jayawardhena et al. 2009). Given this background, a question arises: how do organisations gain permission from consumers so that mobile marketing can become an effective marketing tool? More specifically, what are the factors that influence consumers to subscribe to permission-based mobile marketing?

Uses of Mobiles as Effective Marketing Tools

Information is paramount for the customer and having the right information, at the right time and in the right format could have a positive impact on the customer (Chen et al. 2009). Though there is a risk of giving the customer too much information which may or may not be really useful for them, it is still of great importance that customer have access to and are given the opportunity to have the right to timely information. (Chen et al. 2009). Customers show their willingness to receive mobile message could suggest a possibility of interest and they would keep accepting the message if they are not intrusive, relevant and offer tangible benefit (Hosseini and Ph, 2001, cited by Amarsanaa and Anjorin, 2012).

Various Types of Mobile Marketing

SMS and MMS

Companies use SMS for advertising and communication purposes through SMS, which can also work in both directions. Companies can send messages to a network of mobile users all at once, or on an individual basis, while the company can also receive SMS from their customers, usually opting to participate in a marketing and sales campaign.

MMS marketing is similar to SMS marketing but allows users to send picture messages, videos, or audio (Mobile Marketing Trends, 2012).

According to Bamba and Barnes (2006) there are six ways of using SMS for advertising: brand building, special offers, timely media 'teasers', competitions, polls/voting, products, services and information requests.

Bluetooth

Idwan et al. (2008) states Bluetooth is an industrial specification for wireless Personal Area Networks that provides a way to connect and exchange information between devices, such as mobile phones, laptops, PCs, printers and digital cameras via a secure, low-cost and globally unlicensed short-range radio frequency. A Bluetooth-enabled device uses a radio communication system, so they do not have to be in line of sight of each other, and can even be in other rooms depending on the power class of the product (Idwan et al. 2008).

Mobile Web

Kroski (2008) defines the mobile Web as the World Wide Web which is accessed through a mobile device ranging from a mobile phone to an iPod Touch. It constitutes the entirety of the internet and is not limited to websites which have specifically designed for mobile viewing. Handsets and mobile phones which have Web capabilities can search and browse the internet from anywhere they can get a phone signal.

Mobile Website

For many years, website developers made extensive use of Flash for the sophisticated motion and animation effects it can create. Flash was and is pervasive throughout the Web. However, Flash does not work on Apples iPhone's and iPad's, and works only sporadically on other popular mobile platforms. As such, many mobile users simply can't see images, video or even navigation buttons that are programmed with Flash (Yeh and Fontenelle, 2012).

Location Based Service

A location-based service (LBS) is one that allows an advertiser to send advertisements or other information to a mobile device based on its physical location. Location based services are offered by cell phone networks which are able to track the general location of a mobile phone user through the process of triangulation. If the mobile phone user has their Global position services (GPS) system turned on, that will also serve to identify their location in a much more specific way. Once the network is able to find out where the user is, the advertiser can send out an ad-based on that location (Mobile Marketing Trends, 2012).

Banner ads

Pop-up advertisements are seen with high-traffic websites. When the user clicks on pop-up, separate webpage is opened. Banner advertisements are seen in the form of a rectangular banner. When the user clicks on the banner, they are navigated to a separate window. Banner and pop-up advertisements may contain attractive audio-visual graphics and animations (Mehta et al. 2010).

Mobile Applications

Apps are actual applications that are downloaded and installed on your mobile device, rather than being rendered within a browser. Users visit device-specific portals such as Apple's App Store, Android Market, or Blackberry App World in order to find and download apps for a given operating system. The

app may pull content and data from the Internet, in similar fashion to a website, or it may download the content so that it can be accessed without an Internet connection (Human Service Solutions, 2011).

According to the Mobile Marketing Association (2008) mobile applications are a rapidly developing segment of the global mobile market. They consist of software that runs on a mobile device and performs certain tasks for the user of the mobile phone. Mobile applications are common on most phones, including inexpensive entry-level-models. Their wide use is due to the many functions they perform, including providing user interfaces for basic telephony and messaging services, as well as advanced services such as games and videos.

Mobile applications typically use the mobile phones capabilities, such as its camera, GPS and three dimensional (3D) graphics. These capabilities provide additional opportunities for ad campaigns. For example, if the campaign creators know that a significant percentage of the target population owns handsets with GPS, the ads could use locations information as part of the call to action (Mobile Marketing Association, 2008).

Quick Response Codes

Robinson (2010) explains a QR (Quick Response) code as a two dimensional bar code that can be read on devices such as mobile camera phone, a laptop or other computers. When it is scanned, it allows the user to undertake an action such as reading a text, accessing a website or texting a number. In other words, a QR code links the physical world (poster, printout, room, physical object) to the electronic (web resource) and facilitates communication (SMS, phone call), adding a significant value by improving accessibility to information for those using mobile devices.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims:

- To identify the main methods of mobile marketing used by companies,
- To measure the amount of contact received by customers by companies;
- To determine determine the customers perceptions of mobile marketing;
- To determine how mobile marketing contributes to customer loyalty

4. RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

Research conducted consisted of a survey which was distributed to 100 respondents. The questions were designed around the findings from the in-depth interviews and the research objectives. The researcher decided to use face to face street surveys as it eliminates bias, is time and cost effective, and is relatively simplicity of coding, analysis and interpretation of data collected (Malhotra, 2010).

The research is based upon primary data as the secondary data alone could not help to achieve the research objectives. Therefore, this study can be considered as a questionnaire- based cross sectional study.

Sampling

Method: Non-probability was chosen as not every element of the target population has a chance of being selected because the inclusion or exclusion of elements in a sample. It is left to the discretion of the researcher as long as they are in line with the sampling frame. The researcher has chosen convenience sampling, as it is the most sophisticated non-probability technique.

Sampling Technique: Non-probability convenience sampling was used. This method is a two-stage restricted judgemental sampling which consists of developing quotas of population elements, which the sample element selected based on the judgement of the researcher (Malhotra, 2010).

Sample Size: 100 questionnaires were distributed. This obtained perceptions and attitudes of both genders and eliminated bias. Limitations on time and money had an influence over the sample size (Malhotra, 2010), thus surveys were distributed in the Alwar District

5. DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Demographics of Survey Population

A quota sample of 100 people was taken, using age and gender as quota controls (See table 3 .1). Respondents were asked their gender age category and their ownership of a mobile. Therefore, quotas for each age category were reached, 18-30 (11 percent) 25-30 (10 percent) 31-42 (22 percent), 43-54 (18 percent) 55+ (34 percent) . Of the 100 respondents surveyed all respondents indicated they owned a mobile phone. (7 percent) they had more than one mobile phone.

Figure 1 Level of Male Agreement/Disagreement of Six Statements

5.2 Customers Perceptions of Mobile Marketing

Of the 7 mobile marketing tools listed 100 of the respondents were aware of SMS (100 percent). 63 respondents (63 percent) are aware of Bluetooth, with 58 (58 percent) using it on their mobile phone. 54 respondents (54 percent) are aware of mobile websites (54 percent),but only 31 respondents (31 percent) have noticed them. 47 respondents (47 percent) are aware of QR codes, but only 15 percent have scanned a QR code. 37 respondents (37 percent) are aware of Banner advertisements, but only 16 respondents have used them. 25 respondents (25 percent) are aware of LBM, but 17 respondents (17 percent) have received them. 62 respondents (62 percent) indicated that they are aware of Mobile Apps, and 1 person indicated phone calls as being a mobile marketing tool.

Figure 2 Awareness of Mobile Marketing Tools by Gender

Figure 3 Level of Agreement/Disagreement with Six Statements

The female respondents surveyed showed a greater awareness of mobile marketing tools, apart from banner advertisements where the male respondents had a 3 percent greater awareness. As to be expected the younger generation seem to have a better understanding of mobile marketing tools. The perception of mobile marketing in both genders has generated similar findings, showing 50 percent of respondents agreeing to provide their mobile numbers to companies, with males showing slightly higher willingness than females. However it is also shown by the general population of respondents indicating their perceptions of mobile marketing has improved.

How Mobile Marketing Contributes To Customer Loyalty

Male respondents (56 percent) indicated they receive personalised message from companies over women (44 percent). 'Mobile phones have shown to be very personal devices which may provide firms with unrivalled possibilities to build and maintain one-to-one relationships with their customers' (Camponovo et al., 2005; Siau et al., 2003, cited by ThaeMin, 2007). 52 percent of the total population disagreed with the statement "When I receive offers through my mobile I always use them". Of the 17 percent of those who do use their offers, 12 percent are female.

The ability of consumers to receive marketing messages and offers at any time and based on their location not only reduces their search costs, but also increases their shopping efficiency while perhaps saving them money through discounts or promotions. However, marketing information and offers sent to consumers simply based on their location that they find irrelevant may cause these consumers to think such marketing efforts are annoying and valueless' (Persaud and Azhar, 2012).

54 percent of the total population agreed that their perception of mobile marketing has improved, with only 24 percent of those surveyed indicating that their perception of mobile marketing has not improved. 'Communication is key to any successful relationship; then it can be argued that reaching customers via their mobile phone can ultimately bring some form of satisfaction' (Chen, Hsieh, P.T. et al. 2009 cited by Amarsanaa and Anjorin, 2012).

21 percent of the people agree with the statement "using mobile marketing tool increase my loyalty to a particular company", of that 21 percent 16 percent are female.

46 percent of the respondents disagree with the statement. 40 percent of the total population agree, that mobile marketing tools increases their intention to buy, of this 40 percent, 26 percent are female and 30 percent disagree with this statement. "I have signed up to a number of companies text messaging service".

32 percent of the total population agreed with this statement, 55 percent disagreed with the statement.

Figure 4 Level of Female Agreement/Disagreement with Six Statements

Conclusion

It is evident from both exploratory and descriptive research that mobile marketing is an immense part of companies marketing campaigns. SMS are the leading method, even though it is the oldest mobile marketing tool employed by companies and it is generally the most received by the respondents interviewed.

It seems that the mobile marketing campaigns employed by the companies interviewed are poorly researched and planned. Practices such as the time of day to send out messages seem to be based on the perception of the marketer rather than information gained from customers' feedback. As a result, text messaging campaigns may not be working to their full potential. Companies must set goals and targets with each mobile marketing campaign in order to measure the success of the campaign and address issues that may arise. It is important also that Companies introduce new mobile marketing methods, in order not to fall behind in the latest mobile marketing tools. Companies must also remember to educate their customers on actions required to uncover the messages.

It was shown from the survey results that there is a high level of information being pushed on customers, which may be reflecting the number of people who are unwilling to provide their mobile numbers to companies. Making customers aware that they are signing up to a text messaging service and providing them with a procedure to follow in order to opt out from the service may result in a higher percentage of people willing to provide their numbers, providing the customers with a level of control. Carefully selecting a convenient time and day of the week to contact customers may lower the perception of 'pushed' contact from companies, as information may not feel as intrusive if it is received at a convenient time. In order to avoid aggravating customers, consent should be gotten from customers before adding their mobile numbers to databases, thus companies messages being sent will be well received, leading to customers acting upon the message, resulting in customer loyalty and respectability for the company.

Perceptions of mobile marketing will always have both positive and negative images, and it is up to the individual companies to select and use mobile marketing tools to change customers' minds and to enhance their perception of mobile marketing. Mobile phones are a very personal device, creating a big opportunity for companies to create awareness of their products and services while building a base of loyal customers.

Customer Loyalty is achieved through contact with the customer and providing them with discounts and offers through a personalised medium. This will make the customer feel that they are individually valued by the company and will in turn increase their loyalty. The different mobile marketing tools available are an ideal way for companies to offer these discounts and offers to the correct customers at the appropriate time, and as such these mobile marketing tools will build customer loyalty. This loyalty will help to persuade customers to purchase from the company rather than from a competitor.

Awareness of all the mobile marketing tools available and their capabilities appears to be minimal from the perspective of both companies and respondents.

Bluetooth seems to be a widely used mobile tool with the survey respondents, a tool which companies could utilise more although it is considered an out of date mobile marketing tool. From the industry expert's point of view, few companies are showing interest in QR codes, mobile apps and mobile websites, but SMS are the leading contact tool used by companies followed by Bluetooth, LBM and Banner advertisements. However females have a great awareness of mobile marketing tools, apart from

banner advertisements, with males having nine times greater awareness of these. This is of interest to companies in choosing their mobile marketing tools to target specific market segments.

Companies need to consider optimising their websites or begin introducing mobile websites as the survey results show a significant number of respondents utilise the internet on their mobile phones. Providing customers with the option to gain information on the move will also enhance customer loyalty.

Overall mobile marketing has proven to be a successful marketing tool, which needs some attention in order not to push too much unwanted information on customers. Generally, the perception of mobile marketing has improved and respondents also indicated mobile marketing tools increases their loyalty to companies and increases their intention to buy. Companies also agreed mobile marketing is the way of the future. Indeed the way people are now communicating with each other is changing and it is up to the individual companies to keep up to date with the various mobile marketing tools available.

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8. LIMITATION

The main issue in this study is that this research project only focused on the attitudes towards mobile advertisements in general. It did not include specific product categories as one of the variables which may affect the attitudes of customers towards such products and mobile advertisements.

The data is collected on the basis of convenience sampling so the result can be optimized by including more sample from the city. If the scale for measuring the attitudes is, i.e. is exclusively developed for analyzing the attitudes towards mobile advertisements in the near future, the results may be generalized to the whole population in the city.

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